

Real-world Application Facilitating Trustworthy Human-Robot Collaboration with Innovative Explainable Neuro-symbolic Reasoning

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Abstract—Currently, we may observe closer human-robot collaboration (HRC) in various industrial and everyday use cases. Computer vision, robotics, and machine learning advancements have created new ideas and possibilities for various applications. The progressing and omnipresent need for automation of various aspects of our lives opens new challenges regarding safety and building trust between humans and autonomous robots. Although human-robot collaboration applications allow for increased productivity, safety is still a significant challenge when designing and deploying HRC systems.

Motivated by the challenges and limitations of current approaches to safety and trustworthiness matters, we developed the concept of anomaly detection. By adapting a hybrid AI approach to detect such events, our goal is to increase the safety of the human operator and eventually to improve the trust in the robotic system. Moreover, we believe that such innovative AI-based data analysis approach can lead to more fluent human-robot collaboration and improved productivity without sacrificing safety of the human operators.

Index Terms—deep learning, neuro-symbolic, human-robot collaboration, autonomous robots, hybrid AI

I. INTRODUCTION

Currently, we can observe closer human-robot collaboration (HRC) in various industrial and everyday use cases. Advancements in computer vision, robotics, and machine learning have generated new ideas and possibilities for various applications. There are no doubts, that human-robot collaboration applications enable increased productivity. However, safety remains a significant challenge in designing and deploying such systems.

In particular, collaborative robots can solve a certain tasks in many ways. However, the researchers point out [1] the following operation methods to implement safety mechanisms:

- Conservative collaborative operation method. The interaction between the human and the robot happens when the robot stands still. This improves safety but also slows down the collaboration process.
- Speed and separation monitoring. In such a scenario, sensors can be mounted in the environment in order to monitor fixed areas in the near vicinity of the robot. Such a way of monitoring prevents the contact between the robot and humans entirely.
- Power and force limiting. This approach ensures the safety of a human during a collaboration process, by adjusting biomechanical load (force and pressure) with respect to human proximity.
- Passive hand-guiding operations. In this scenario, the human operator instructs the robot to perform different tasks by simply hand guiding it to pick up a part and move it into the desired position following a path.

In this work, we propose new innovative neuro-symbolic AI-based data analysis approach to increase safety of human operators in real-life robotics ecosystem.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: related work is analyzed in Section II. In section III we provide an overview of the architecture of the proposed innovative hybrid AI approach to anomaly detection for human-robot collaboration. In Section III we detail the proposed architecture and our innovative hybrid AI solution. Experiments, datasets description and ablation studies are provided in Section IV, while conclusions are given thereafter.

II. RELATED WORK

Depending on the use case, the autonomous robot may be expected to behave in a socially acceptable manner and to be capable of sensing human intentions, actions, and states. Researchers often distinguish [2] between human-robot interaction (HRI) and human-robot collaboration (HRC). The HRI considers interactivity between humans and robots, while HRC is focused on humans and robots working together to achieve a common goal.

In the literature, the mainstream research is intuitively focusing on human motion recognition and tracking. Particularly, in [3], the authors have observed that more than half of the reviewed methods rely on human detection and/or tracking.

Pose estimation is a task in the field of computer vision aiming at detecting and tracking human pose in 2D and 3D space [4]. In general, this is realized by predicting the position of specific body parts [5]. Models used for this task predict the localization of key joints such as shoulders, elbows, wrists, hips, knees, and ankles within static image or motion video. Since the motion of specific parts of the human body can be predicted and associated with specific human actions, understanding the body pose is essential for tasks such as action recognition and video understanding.

Besides the fact, that pose estimation techniques can be categorized into 2D and 3D estimation, they can fall into the bottom-up [6] and top-down categories of methods. In bottom-up approaches [7], individual body joints are initially identified and then tracked to estimate a complete pose. Top-down methods firstly detect a person and then estimate body joints within the detected bounding boxes.

Differences between 2D and 3D pose estimation depend on the source image or video material used for this task. 2D estimation is carried out in two-dimensional space, while 3D estimation requires complementary depth-related information, obtained with the use of additional sensors, such as RGB cameras, LiDAR, 3D scanners or inertial measurement data (information about dynamics, obtained by e.g. accelerometer and gyroscope).

In the literature, human-collaboration systems often rely heavily on accurate human pose estimation. Particularly, in [8], authors have proposed a Separable-Sparse Graph Convolutional Network (SeS-GCN) for pose forecasting.

Following that line of research, we may identify various methods and techniques applied for anomaly detection. In particular, in [9], the authors considered various deep learning-based methods for anomaly detection in human-robot Collaboration applications. They also highlighted the challenges related to multimodal anomaly detection based on observation of human and robot behavior.

Hereby, we further explore the field by innovative neuro-symbolic AI approach, as presented in detail in the next sections.

III. THE PROPOSED INNOVATIVE HYBRID AI SOLUTION

In this section, we provide an overview of the architecture of the proposed hybrid AI approach to anomaly detection. First,

we define the rationale behind its design and continue with the description of particular technologies and components used.

A. Architectural design assumptions

The primary objective of the proposed solution is to combine multiple sources to enhance anomaly detection in human-machine interaction. This involves leveraging knowledge about the underlying process and the surrounding environment. Additionally, the utilisation of symbolic AI plays a vital role in anomaly detection. In that regard, we made the following design assumptions:

- The entire approach relies on existing and pre-trained deep learning algorithms in order to segment and understand the visual inputs.
- In order to identify the situations that might be dangerous for humans, we leverage domain knowledge related to the human-robot collaboration process (e.g., good practices and safety guidelines).
- One of the goals is to limit the amount of effort related to the data annotation process.
- We want the entire processing pipeline to be fully differentiable (from the anomaly signals down to deep neural network throughout the encoded knowledge) so that, in the back-propagation process, the system may adapt and finally infer what elements of the analysed visual content cause the dangerous situation.

B. The Concept of Anomaly in Human-Robot Collaboration

There are different definitions and approaches to tackle the anomaly detection problems. In our case, as the anomaly, we consider and need to detect one of the following events (see also Table 1):

- Violation of the safety guidelines (e.g., human standing with back facing to the robot, a person entered a restricted area) since protecting humans is the most crucial priority.
- Interruptions in the assembly process (e.g., a human operator drops an item).
- Operators' safety signals (e.g. emergency stops body gestures).
- Anomalies in human and robot activities (e.g., unusual human behaviors reflected in activities or gestures).

Some of the examples depicting the anomalies in the context of human-robot collaboration have been shown in Fig. 2.

C. Architecture

The general architecture of the proposed hybrid approach is presented in 1. Here, we combine deep neural networks with probabilistic symbolic programs.

Unlike other hybrid AI approaches, we work on an intermediate representation of the scene provided by several different deep neural network models.

We explain them in more detail in the next section devoted to understanding scenes using computer vision. The information from different models and sensors is combined by means of the neural network, which constitutes multiple dense layers followed by ReLU activations or Softmax layers.

Fig. 1. Information flow used by the proposed approach.

Fig. 2. Example of anomalies recorded during human-robot collaboration process (Human in the robot working area, Emergency Stop Gesture, Process interruption - dropped item)

The last layer (the output of the DNN model) provides so-called symbols for the probabilistic program. Each symbol represents a different fact (or combination of facts) about the observed scene. In the current approach, we considered a different number of symbols that refer to human activity, current robot state (e.g., of a UR10 robot arm or Mobile robot), human pose orientation (e.g., with respect to fixed objects like tables or desks), or mutual distances between humans and robot(s).

In the final stage of the proposed pipeline, we apply symbolic programs that are intended to flag anomalous and dangerous situations. In our case, the probabilistic programs are written in ProbLog [10] programming language and integrated into the proposed architecture by means of the DeepProbLog framework [11]. We chose DeepProbLog since it provides a good flexibility in developing domain rules and constraints.

D. Scene Understanding

In our opinion and experience, to develop a successful scene understanding (focused on HRC aspects), we require the following elements:

- Human sensing, including 3D location and body pose.
- Robot sensing, including its 3D location, current state, goals, and planned movement.
- 3D spatiotemporal correlation of humans and robots.

Therefore, our approach to scene understanding relies on multi-dimensional heterogeneous data sources and various deep neural network models that analyse the data obtained. Particularly, our goal in that process is to identify the human activity as well as the robot arm position.

More precisely, we propose to use the following techniques:

- Odometry and forward kinematics to precisely track robot movements.
- Depth maps and point clouds obtained from Realsense cameras to perform distance measurements.
- Different variants of PoseNet architectures to regress human pose in 2D.
- ROMP [12] (Monocular, One-stage, Regression of Multiple 3D People) human pose regressor to obtain human body position and relevant parts (limbs) orientation (e.g., hands, torso, legs, etc.). It relies on SMPL [13] human body model.
- Fast RCNN [14] for object detection and tracking (e.g., to contextualise human activities by recognising various objects located in the near vicinity or to track robot elements).
- Semantic segmentation for precise object mask extraction (e.g., human), which can be further combined with depth maps.

Fig. 3. Example of occlusions along with correct human pose regression (In most of the cases the human body is always clipped either by robot arm or elements building the workspace).

E. Human 3D Tracking

During the developments, we encountered several challenges related to the actual setup of the sensors and vision systems used in the real-world case scenario.

For example, in the early stages, there was only one camera looking at the operator during the human-robot collaboration process. This eliminated a vast majority of efficient and effective methods for multi-view human pose estimation.

Moreover, adding more cameras, in complex industrial setups did not solve all the problems. Particularly, it was impossible to avoid the occlusion, which significantly complicated the object detection and human pose regression. More precisely, in the close human-robot collaboration, the robot arm occludes the human operator while delivering and removing the items. Some other challenges imposed by the environment have been depicted in Fig. 3.

F. Spatio-temporal data alignment

Using various data sources, we were able to obtain a comprehensive view of the analysed scene. However, this process requires detailed information about the installed sensors and their internal parameters.

Relying on multiple sources is crucial to synchronising them so that the adequate data frames arrive at the right time. Moreover, it is important to know the intrinsic and extrinsic parameters of all of the cameras.

In general the proposed procedure is as follows:

- Extract intrinsic camera parameters (e.g., focal lengths, lens distortions).
- Extract extrinsic camera parameters (e.g., position and rotation with respect to the world coordinate system).
- Extract the robot's odometry and obtain the robot's positions and poses (in the case of PIAP UC, there are two robots – the mobile one and the UR10 arm).
- Obtain 3D human poses and align them with the depth map.
- Extract other predictions from object detection methods and align them with the depth map.
- Combine all the depth measurements with the camera positions and rotations (in order to calculate 3D estimates with respect to the global coordinate system).
- Synchronise all the information using the ROSbag time stamp.

Fig. 4. Example of full scene reconstruction (there are views from three cameras and the image demonstrating 3D reconstruction)

G. Knowledge-based Reasoning

Currently, the goal of the developed neuro-symbolic rules is to allow for expressing the safety best practices and to recognise any dangerous or anomalous moments, as it has been explained in the previous sections.

In particular, the rules for normal and abnormal states are based on safety best practices for UR10 human-robot collaboration. In general, the recommendation always says to track the robot's movements. In our case, due to the robot's location and the natural assembly process, the particular danger is the moment when the robot delivers the box with elements to the table. However, the rule triggers the anomaly only when the human is not following the robot arm. This can be indicated by current human activity. Particularly when the human is rotated toward the wall and has the robot arm behind the back, then the symbolic rules trigger an alarm.

In the proposed approach, we use several DeepProbLog to represent various rules and constraints related to physics and facts concerning the human-robot collaboration process. More precisely, we have:

- a set of rules responsible for providing the probability of anomaly given the probabilistic symbols we obtain from the visual scene understanding component.
- a set of rules for confirming that the currently observed part of the collaboration process can be considered normal.
- a set of rules (that could also be a part of a loss function) that allows for capturing and penalising illegal responses from the deep neural network (e.g., some of the human and robot states are mutually exclusive).
- a set of rules that captures facts about the environment (e.g., the assembly process takes place at the table).
- a set of rules that allow to express human gestures (e.g., emergency stop gestures).

In traditional propositional logic, the body is composed of facts that are represented as Boolean variables. In our case, they have associated probabilities. More specifically, the output of the symbolic rule is the probability of particular symbols' concatenation.

Fig. 5. Example rule for Human in the Working Area warning/anomaly (R and H indicate robot's and human skeletons respectively)

An example illustrating this is shown in Fig. 5. This rule, named “anomaly”, has a “head”, which takes two variables (H and R, which represent human and robot skeletons, respectively) and one constant (the warning message). From the Boolean logic standpoint, this rule will be triggered when two statements are true, namely “ur10 is at the assembling table” and “human is in the working area”. However, because the engine is probabilistic, this rule will actually answer the question, “Given the human and robot 3D skeletons, what is the probability that the human is in the robot working area?”.

Probabilistic symbols

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limb_state(Skeleton, Y, 'arms spread')
limb_state(Skeleton, Y, 'left arm flexion')
limb_state(Skeleton, Y, 'right arm flexion')
limb_state(Skeleton, Y, 'left arm height')
limb_state(Skeleton, Y, 'right arm height')
limb_state(Skeleton, Y, 'left leg flexion')
limb_state(Skeleton, Y, 'right leg flexion')
limb_state(Skeleton, Y, 'left thigh flexion')
limb_state(Skeleton, Y, 'right thigh flexion')

```

Fig. 6. Probabilistic symbols representing states of human limbs – used for human pose recognition

In the proposed approach, the neural components shown in Fig. 6 are intended to model human and robot activities and current states.

More precisely, we use the considered deep neural networks to encode the visual inputs as probabilistic symbols. In such

a manner, we use probabilistic symbols to recognise human body poses and gestures. In the example shown in Fig. 6, we use several neural networks to analyse the state of human limbs. Each neural network returns categorical output with a probability (e.g., $p(\text{'wide'})=0.9$ for the “arms spread” symbol).

Another example is shown in Fig. 7. It can be explained (thanks to the probabilistic symbols) that the T-POSE is recognised because because the arms are wide spread, we do not see bends in both of the arms, and both are moderately high. The meaning of the symbols (e.g., wide, no-band, etc.) are established during the networks training process.

H. Gradient-based Differentiable Training

Integrating symbolic background knowledge with gradient-based differentiable machine learning is a well-known challenge. One potential way to address it efficiently is to use the Sentential Decision Diagrams (SDDs). The SDD can be considered as a data structure for representing Boolean functions. The SDDs support a number of efficient operations for constructing and manipulating Boolean functions. SDDs attract attention because they are concise and support many useful queries and transformations that are adapted to neuro-symbolic-based approaches.

In the proposed approach, the visual input (and sensory data from robots) first goes via deep neural networks and then (as facts associated with probabilities) is processed in probabilistic programs to produce final outputs/predictions. During supervised training, we contradict these predictions with the ground truth labels in order to calculate loss values. Because both of the frameworks use a similar concept of transforming the domain knowledge and constraints into an arithmetic circuit, it is possible to propagate the errors (gradients) back to obtain the deep neural network weights updates.

Moreover using PSDD, we may leverage the concept of semantic loss, which allows to define the constraints in propositional logic. Semantic loss in this context measures the logical consistency and correctness of the output produced by the neural network. It is encouraging the neural network to produce outputs that align with the rules of propositional logic. In our case, different sets of rules constitute different probabilistic programs. Each program serves a different purpose. Apart from one for anomaly detection (e.g., propositional logic can be used to flag anomalous situations based on facts extracted from observed scenes), we have another program that is intended to confirm that the human does not violate any safety guidelines and one for checking the physics-related constraints (e.g., a robot cannot deliver or remove items simultaneously).

In the proposed approach we use DeepProbLog. This way, we offload the computational burden related to PSDD circuit generation and delegate it to the DeepProbLog framework. It is an extension of ProbLog that integrates Probabilistic Logic Programming with deep learning by introducing the neural predicate. More precisely, the neural predicate represents probabilistic facts, which probabilities are calculated

Fig. 7. Example of T-POSE gesture recognition along with 3D reconstruction, program/rule structure, program output and explanation

(inferred) by neural networks. The benefit of using Deep-ProbLog (in contrast to the vanilla PSDD approach) is the fact that it unlocks the expressive probabilistic-logical modeling and reasoning (e.g., ProbLog languages allow for defining very complex programs) and by complying with well-known PyTorch framework, it allows for seamless integration into the existing machine learning pipelines.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

A. Datasets

In the experiments we have used two different datasets.

The first one, has been developed during the research activities in the ULTIMATE project. It has been recorded as ROS bag files. There are different parts of the recordings capturing different activities of the human-robot collaboration.

The second dataset is CMU Panoptic Dataset. It is mostly used to train the human activities detection. This dataset records diverse subjects performing different activities. The dataset has been recorder with multiple cameras, which allowed for precise extraction of the 3D human skeletons. In our case, we focused on these activities which resemble the one recorded for the considered HRC use case. This way, we avoided the need to develop our own dataset, which would contain high-quality 3D skeletons.

B. Evaluation metrics

To assess the performance, we have used the standard metrics for comparing classification effectiveness, namely:

- Precision = $\frac{TP}{TP+FP}$
- Recall (Sensitivity) = $\frac{TP}{TP+FN}$
- Specificity = $\frac{TN}{TN+FP}$
- Balanced Accuracy = $\frac{Sensitivity+Specificity}{2}$
- F1-score = $2 * \frac{Precision*Recall}{Precision+Recall}$

In the above equations, TP , FP , FN , TN indicate True Positive, False Positive, False Negative, and True Negative, respectively. TP (True Positive) is the number of anomalous cases correctly classified as such. FN (False Negative) is the number of anomalous cases incorrectly classified as normal ones. FP (False Positive) is the number of normal cases that are incorrectly identified as anomalies, and TN (True Negative) is the number of normal cases correctly classified as such.

C. Anomaly detection performance

In this section, we describe and discuss the quality of anomaly detection, which is related to violations of safety guidelines.

In Figure 8 we show an example of such a violation being detected using the proposed neuro-symbolic approach. The image shows the situation recorded by the camera in the workshop. The wireframe view in the top left corner is depicting the human skeleton and the robot arm above, which constitutes the output of spatio-temporal alignment. The image on the right records the same situation but from a different camera located outside the workshop. In this case, the anomaly alarm was triggered because the UR10 position was above the workshop table where the workers assembled the items. This position of the robot effectively blocks the path to the loading area.

In order to give a quantitative assessment of the anomaly detection performance, we compared the obtained results with:

- baseline neural-only approach, which approximates the output (anomalies), but ignores the symbolic knowledge
- Neuroplex-based model, which approximates knowledge with additional neural networks [15]

Fig. 8. Example of safety guidelines violation (3D reconstruction, Camera view with visualisations, and anomaly type recognition)

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF PERFORMANCE METRICS (BAC-BALANCED ACCURACY, AUC-AREA UNDER THE ROC CURVE, AND F1 SCORE) FOR ANOMALY, ROBOT, AND HUMAN ACTIVITY RECOGNITION.

	BAC	AUC	F1
Proposed (28k param.)	0.999	0.999	0.998
Neuroplex-based [15]	0.998	0.999	0.964
Proposed (10k param.)	0.726	0.920	0.805
Baseline (ANN)	0.997	0.997	0.909

For all of the methods, anomaly detection is a binary classification problem. In the evaluation process, we adapted the metrics described in the previous section. It can be noted that in most of the cases Neuroplex-like method performs similarly to our approach and the differences are marginal. However, for the Neuroplex, there is an extra burden to train the neural approximator that will mimic the knowledge reasoning.

D. Neuro-symbolic human (anomalous) activity detection

In this section we evaluated the quality of neuro-symbolic approach to human activity detection. For that purpose we used one part of our dataset where various (also anomalous) workers activities have been recorded. The annotations in the dataset contains name of an activity and frame ranges. Therefore, we may compare the prediction obtained from our hybrid approach with the ground-truth. It must be noted that we have used only external data sources to train the model.

From the table II, it can be observed that there is still room for improvement in such activities as squatting and bending. This happens due to the fact that both activities are quite similar to each other. Similarly, “hi gesture” (Hi-POSE) is also confused raised hand and thus it has so low recall rate.

TABLE II
PERFORMANCE METRICS BY CLASS

Class	BAC	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	Specificity
BENT	0.692	0.222	0.400	0.286	0.985
Hi-POSE	0.583	1.000	0.167	0.286	1.000
L+R-UP	0.948	0.933	0.902	0.917	0.993
LH-UP	0.959	0.920	0.920	0.920	0.998
RH-UP	0.994	0.476	1.000	0.645	0.988
SQUAT	0.667	1.000	0.333	0.500	1.000
T-POSE	0.881	0.750	0.771	0.760	0.990

Fig. 9. Example of detected human activities (T-POSE, Raised hands, Bent/Squat)

E. Ablation studies

In this section, we detail the experiments and comment on the results, which are intended to verify the following research question: “Can we extract information about human or robot activities from the context, thus reducing the amount of required training data?”

In other words, given that we have identified an anomaly in complying with safety guidelines, to what extent can we be certain about the current activities of both robots and humans?

Such capability of the proposed neuro-symbolic hybrid solution would indicate that the system can learn about elements that are not explicitly labelled in the dataset. Obviously, this benefit will be achieved thanks to the domain knowledge encoded as a probabilistic neuro-symbolic program.

In the considered experiment, we expressed the robot and activities as probabilistic symbols where humans can be idling, assembling, or observing (waiting for) the robot to deliver/remove items from the table. Similarly, robot activities are also modelled with probabilistic symbols indicating the robot is either delivering, removing, or idling. In contrast to the previous sections, we used our dataset and adapted a random split (70% for training and 30% for testing). The adapted portion of the dataset includes only the UR10 robot and a

TABLE III

ABLATION STUDIES COMPARING BALANCED ACCURACY AND PoCR FOR DIFFERENT SUBSETS OF SYMBOLIC PROGRAMS (AD-ANOMALY DETECTION; ND-NORMAL SITUATION DETECTION, EC-ENVIRONMENTAL CONSTRAINTS, SL-SEMANTIC LOSS).

Used programs	Anomaly	Human	Robot	PoCR
	BAC	BAC	BAC	
AD	0.998	0.536	0.441	0.041
AD+ND	0.999	0.500	0.875	0.040
AD+ND+EC	0.999	0.936	0.874	0.041
AD+ND+EC+SL	0.999	0.939	0.874	0.999

single human worker.

In the experiment we used balanced accuracy metrics (BAC) to compare different setups. More precisely, we use several neuro-symbolic programs to represent various rules and constraints related to physics and facts concerning the human-robot collaboration process:

- AD (Anomaly Detection) is responsible for providing the probability of anomaly given the probabilistic symbols we obtain from the visual scene understanding component.
- ND (Normality Detection) is responsible for confirming that the currently observed part of the collaboration process can be considered normal.
- SL (Semantic Loss) is ensuring the correctness of responses (e.g. robot activities alike delivering and removing are mutually exclusive).
- EC (Environmental Constraints) captures facts about the environment (e.g. returns probability that a human is at the assembling table).

Moreover, we designed the PoCR (Percentage of Correct Responses) metric, which indicates how many neural network responses obey the physical and environmental constraints defined by the EC and SL neuro-symbolic programs. In other words, PoCR allows us to identify if the training process is consistent with the defined symbolic rules.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper outlines the neuro-symbolic reasoning methods designed and developed to facilitate human-robot collaboration scenarios. From the scientific point of view, the most relevant aspect is that we split the processing into visual scene understanding and knowledge-based reasoning. The first extracts information from various sources (including cameras, depth-sensing units, and odometry), while the second adapts domain expert knowledge to perform reasoning related to anomaly detection. Moreover, to improve the robustness, the architectural design also includes out-of-distribution detection capabilities.

To show the usefulness of the proposed approach, we have included different experiments, which are intended to assess qualitative and quantitative aspects of various detection and recognition mechanisms used in the proposed approach. Apart from classical performance assessment, we also dived into assessing the benefits of the hybrid approach.

The promising results open the space for further improvements and developments within the HRC context. As a future

work, we plan to particularly focus on extending explainability capabilities and performance improvements.

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